

AN INVESTIGATION INTO FIRST-YEAR STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS OF LEARNER AUTONOMY THROUGH PROJECT-BASED LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The study employed a survey design in which quantitative data was collected. A questionnaire consisting of 24 questions was distributed to 94 first-year non-English major students to understand their perceptions of learner autonomy through Project-based learning at Ton Duc Thanh university. The data was considered with the support of SPSS software version 20. The data analysis showed that students held positive perceptions in all four dimensions of learner autonomy, namely initiating, monitoring, evaluating and using ICTs in learning process. This finding, accordingly, suggests a significant effect of Project-based learning on learner autonomy.

Keywords: Learner autonomy, project-based learning, perceptions of learner autonomy, first-year non-English major students.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

In the past, traditional teaching methods like Grammar Translation were widely applied in English classrooms in which teachers played the main role of knowledge dispensers and students passively absorbed what their teachers imparted. "In traditional view of education, teachers serve as the source of knowledge while learners serve as passive receivers" (Kuzu, 2007). These methods, however, could not exploit students' potential of learning a language to the fullest extent because of the passive patterns of learning. According to Bass (2008), the centeredness of teachers in the classroom can lead to the failure in "nurturing students who can learn through multiple forms of input".

The absolute necessity of improving the teaching and learning issue was a driving force for remarkable changes in the pedagogical field. Accordingly, it is easily seen that there has been a shift from teacher-centered approach to student-centered approach in language teaching and learning where students are "independent and self-directed learners" (Kuzu, 2007). This new learning approach has been proved effective and useful in certain aspects.

The shift from teacher-led pedagogical strategy to student-lead approach has led to the fact that the common practice of getting students in groups or in pairs in the classrooms to share the work is widely employed. Project-based learning (PBL), known as the process of learning through the implementation of a group project, is utterly not a new concept. According to Stoller (2002), in PBL, "students are actively engaged in information gathering, processing and reporting over a period of

time”. PBL, therefore, activates students’ latent potential for learning and results in “increased content knowledge and language mastery” (Stoller, 2002).

Due to multiple benefits of PBL, this approach has gained its increasing popularity in any educational settings. Especially, at the level of tertiary education, PBL is always of much higher frequency for the purpose of promoting student’s independence, autonomy and accountability. In particular, at Ton Duc Thang university (TDTU), PBL has just been introduced in the school curriculum since the first semester of the school year 2018 – 2019. Apparently, first-year students have just had their first-hand experience in PBL at the school in the first semester.

With the aim of investigating into how first-year students perceive learner autonomy in PBL, the study entitled “*An investigation into first-year students’ perceptions of learner autonomy through project-based learning*” was conducted.

1.2 Project-based learning at TDTU

At TDTU, all students are required to work in groups of four to conduct a project in every English class. The topics are different for each level; however, the approaches to the projects are the same. The topics of group projects are taken from units that students have learnt in Keynote books which are official English textbooks of the school. Students can make their own choice for their approaches to the general topic. During the course, teachers strictly track students’ progress in doing the project and provide them with immediate support and guidance when necessary. Then, students are supposed to make an oral presentation with prepared slides on the final day of the course. In the presentation, students answer the questions assigned in the topic and show their personal opinions and critical thinking. The oral assignment is divided evenly among group members.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Project-based learning

2.1.1 Definitions of Project-based learning

PBL is defined as a strategy to create “independent thinkers and learners” (Bell, 2010). In this sense, those involved in PBL will have the chance to explore the real world by creating their own approaches to the problems and solving them using a variety of learning strategies. According to Grant (2002), PBL is an instructional method which focuses on learner-centeredness, giving learners the opportunity to explore “in-depth investigations of worthy topics”. Similarly, Wurdinger (2007) defines PBL as ‘a constructivist pedagogy intent on bringing about deep learning by allowing learners to use an inquiry based on approach to engage in issues and questions that are real and relevant to their lives”. On the other hand, Markham (2011) proposes that PBL integrates “knowing” and “doing” in the way that not only can students learn knowledge and elements of the core curriculum, but also apply what they know to solve authentic problems and produce results that matter. Furthermore, Buck Institute for Education (2017) provides a more formal definition of PBL as follows: “In PBL, students gain knowledge and skills by working for an extended period of time to investigate and respond to an authentic, engaging and complex question, problem, or challenge”.

From the mutual points withdrawn from these aforementioned definitions, it can be concluded that the crux of PBL lies on “student-centeredness”, “real” and “authentic”. Therefore, PBL can be restated as an educational method in which students actively take control over their learning and have a constructive investigation into an authentic problem which is closely related to their lives.

2.1.2 Features of Project-based learning

According to Thomas (2000), there are five main criteria of PBL which are centrality, driving question, constructive investigations, autonomy and realism. Firstly, the centrality of PBL refers to the fact that PBL is the center of the curriculum. In this sense, PBL is the central teaching strategy employed by the teachers and students learn the main concepts of the curriculum through PBL. Secondly, the hallmark of PBL is driving questions that students have to work out in collaboration with their peers. According to Krajcik and MamlokNaaman (2006), a driving question is “a well-designed question that students and teachers elaborate, explore and answer throughout a project”. “A well-designed question” has several key elements should be (1) “feasible” in the way that students can create an inquiry to answer the question, (2) “worthwhile” in the way that it is enjoyable, attractive and inspiring to students, (3) “contextualized” in the way that it is closely related to the real world and students’ life experience, (4) “meaningful” in the way that it is important and useful and (5) “ethical” in the way that it is morally correct and acceptable and does no harm to individuals as well as the environment. Thirdly, in PBL, students are involved in “a constructive investigation”. Constructive investigations embody ‘inquiry, knowledge building and resolution’. Through constructive investigations, students develop their critical thinking. All the skills further prepare students for their future life. Fourthly, Projects are student-driven to some significant degree. This means that the majority of the project work is done by students. However, it does not mean that the role of the teacher is overshadowed. Teachers still play a supportive role as facilitators who provide students with guidance and immediate support when necessary. Through collaborative approach, students gain mutual access to a problem to figure out the problem. Lastly, projects are realistic, not school-like. In PBL, there is a specific topic or problem that requires students to work out. Students are exposed to authentic problems and real-life challenges when they conduct projects and finalize the final product.

The Buck Institute of Education (2017) has introduced eight crucial elements of project work. Accordingly, a work is called project when it has the following features:

Key knowledge, understanding and success skills. A project work should cover key content which is intended to boost students towards their learning goals. Moreover, a project should target at equipping students with essential skills for their lifelong success such as critical thinking, collaboration and self-management.

Challenging problem or question. This feature is the same as “driving question” that functions as a motive for students in PBL. The challenging problem or question should be appropriate and meaningful so that students can work out the solutions.

Sustained inquiry. The students conduct a nonstop investigation into the challenging problem or question. In this case, students have to find multiple resources to approach the problem.

Authenticity. A project should be realistic and closely related to students’ real world. That project should be also engaging to arouse students’ interests.

Student voice and choice. Students are supposed to present orally what they have done as a final product.

Reflection. Students reflect on the continued process of project implementation in terms of difficulties, effectiveness and challenges.

Critique and revision. Constructive comments and feedback are given to student so that they can improve the next project product.

Public product. Students' products are displayed at a specific time in class so that other students can have a cross look around.

In general, PBL lays an emphasis on student-centeredness and this student-led pedagogy highlights the importance of students' self-development of 21st century skills for success in the long run.

2.1.3 Steps in Project-based learning in EFL classes

Thomas (2000) proposed that there are three main phases in making a project which include a beginning, middle and an end. In the initial planning stage, the teacher decides on the selection of the topic and then helps students to develop questions for their investigation into the project. In the middle stage, students construct the project themselves among group members. During this stage, the teacher provides students with necessary support such as resources, advice, and ideas. However, the main work is laid on the students. In the last phase, the product of the project is finalized and evaluated. The teacher may create a culminating event through which students can share their work with other groups and learn from each other.

The three general phases of project implementation can be divided into ten small steps with specific details suggested by Stoller (2002). This ten-step sequence of project work "gives easy-to-manage structure to project work and guides teachers and students in developing meaningful projects that facilitate content learning and provide opportunities for explicit language instruction at critical moments in the project" (Stoller, 2002). This revised model gives more emphasis on the students' role in the process of PBL. However, there are still some stages in which teachers take the role of guiders and facilitators. Below are the steps to conduct a project in PBL.

Agree on a theme for the project.

Determine the final outcome.

Structure the project.

Prepare students for the language demands of step 5.

Gather information.

Prepare students for the language demands of step 7.

Compile and analyze information.

Prepare students for the language demands of step 9.

Present the final product.

Evaluate the project.

The first three steps (1, 2 and 3) are the planning steps that are very crucial in PBL because they help to set specific learning outcomes in the project for the students as well as determine the frame of the project. The language intervention steps (4, 6, 8) aims to provide students with language support throughout the project. These language inputs help students have the right direction in the language use in the project presentation. Step 5 and Step 7 are the two mains steps in the project in which students gather, compile and analyze information critically. Step 10 is product presentation when students are supposed to publish their work and share with the teacher and other classmates. The last step (10) includes evaluation part in which teacher's feedback is given to project products made by the students.

2.2 Learner Autonomy

2.2.1 Definitions of Learner Autonomy

Little (2004) stated that learner autonomy (LA) is “learning how to learn intentionally”. According to him, autonomy empowers students to be “independent, self-reliant and accountable for their own learning”. Likewise, Boud (1988) assumed that students who have LA usually do and understand “beyond usual instructions” given by their teachers. Similarly, Wenden (1991) pointed out that LA is considered as the ability to know how to learn and control learning activities. Moreover, he added, autonomous students show their intentions to discover knowledge themselves with little assistance from other instructors.

Although there are various definitions of LA shared by different authors, linguists and researchers, the core value of LA lies in the fact that LA is the capability of the learner to take responsibility for learning with little aid from teachers and instructors.

2.2.2 Learner Autonomy in EFL classrooms

According to Benson (2003), there are four perspectives of LA which are psychological perspective, technical perspective, political-critical perspective and social-cultural perspective. The first perspective of LA, psychological perspective, focuses on personal attributes of learners including their emotional and mental characteristics. Regarding technical perspective, students’ autonomy and independence are promoted based on situational conditions for learning. The third perspective, political-critical perspective, features students’ control over their access to the content of learning. Lastly, social-cultural perspective, students can promote their learner autonomy through social contexts and interactions.

2.2.3 Dimensions of Learner Autonomy in EFL classrooms

There is a wide range of dimensions of LA according to researchers across the continents. In his research, Kaur (2010) conducted a survey on students’ perceptions towards LA in terms of *Planning, Organizing, Monitoring, Evaluating* their learning and the ability in participating in asynchronous online learning.

In the meanwhile, Humphreys and Myatt (2013) conducted an action research to explore students’ perceptions of learner autonomy and their autonomous experiences regarding *Goal setting development and Self-reflection*.

On the other hand, in Vietnamese context, Dang (2012) measured learner autonomy of students in four different universities in terms of four different aspects namely *Monitoring learning processes, Goal-setting and evaluating learning, Using ICTs (Information in learning, and Initiating learning opportunities*.

In summary, there are a number of dimensions of LA that researchers have investigated into such as Planning, Organizing, Monitoring, Controlling, Organizing, Goal setting development, Self-reflection, Evaluating, and Using ICTs in learning process, etc. All dimensions proposed by the researchers mentioned above have some common viewpoint. Therefore, they may be grouped into four common dimensions namely Initiating, Monitoring, Evaluating and Using ICTs in learning process.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research question

The study aimed at answering the question: What are first-year students' perceptions of learner autonomy through Project-based learning at TDTU?

3.2 Research participants

The participants selected for the study 94 first-year students from three classes at different levels at TDTU. The sampling strategy used in the study was convenience sampling because the target participants were students in classes that the researcher was in charge of. All of the students are aged 18, majoring in IT (34%), Pharmacy (31,9%) and Social studies (24.1%). The majority of students are males (67/94), accounting for 71.3% the total number of participants.

The target population of the study is non-English major first-year university students at TDTU who have just been undergoing the very first changes in textbooks and assessment in the first semester of the school year 2018 – 2019. First-year students at TDTU were targeted in the study because they have just undergone the implementation of PBL in the first semester for the first time. Moreover, the tertiary education is totally different from their high school, meaning that students no longer rely on teachers for knowledge but they have to conduct projects for their own learning; therefore, it was hypothesized that PBL may have significantly affected first-year students' learning autonomy in certain ways, which was the trigger for the initiation of the study.

3.3 Research instruments

The instrument employed in the study was a questionnaire that consists of 24 questions items in form of a five-point Likert scale with five options for each item: (1) strongly disagree, (2) disagree, (3) uncertain, (4) agree, (5) strongly agree. The four dimensions of LA are covered in the questionnaire namely *Initiating learning process*, *Monitoring learning process*, *Evaluating learning process* and *Using ICTs in learning process*.

There are two main parts in the questionnaire in which part A is about background information (4 questions), part B (20 questions) asks students about their perceptions of of four dimensions of learner autonomy through project-based learning in terms. There are five question items for each dimension in this section.

3.4 Data collection procedure

The data was collected from the questionnaire delivered to 94 first-year non-English major students and then analyzed using SPSS version 20 to calculate descriptive statistics.

4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Below is the detailed description of data collected from the questionnaire. According to the statistics in the table, the mean of the cluster is 4.01, which is far from 1 and close to 5. This shows that students tend to agree that PBL has a positive effect on their autonomy.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of students' perceptions of LA through PBL

Dimensions of LA	Question items	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Initiating learning process	5.1 I am aware of the importance of English learning.	94	3	5	4.54
	5.2 I can identify goals in learning English.	94	3	5	4.32
	5.3 I try to find many learning methods to improve English.	94	1	5	3.72
	5.4 I look for every opportunity to use English as much as possible.	94	1	5	3.83
	5.5 I study English voluntarily.	94	2	5	4.22
Monitoring learning process	6.1 I know the most suitable method and use it.	94	2	5	4.13
	6.2 I maintain my timetable to learn English.	94	3	5	4.41
	6.3 I study English both inside and outside the classroom.	94	1	5	3.55
	6.4 I make good use of resources to learn English at home.	94	1	5	3.77
	6.5 I notice my mistakes and learn from them.	94	2	5	4.34
Evaluating learning process	7.1 I reflect on what I have learnt to know the main content.	94	2	5	3.79
	7.2 I can self-evaluate my progress in learning English.	94	2	5	3.81
	7.3 I know my strengths and weaknesses.	94	1	5	4.24
	7.4 I try to improve my weaknesses.	94	1	5	3.46
	7.5 I try to develop my strengths.	94	3	5	4.47
Using ICTs in learning	8.1 I use computer applications to learn	94	3	5	4.04

Dimensions of LA process	Question items	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
	8.2 I listen to news and songs in English on the Internet.	94	3	5	4.37
	8.3 I check my proficiency by doing progress tests online.	94	1	5	3.44
	8.4 I check my English level by comparing it with the skills of others on the Internet.	94	1	5	3.65
	8.5 I make friends on the Internet to practice English.	94	1	5	4.11
Average					4.01

In addition, among the four perspectives of LA, the mean for Initiating leaning process is the biggest while that of Using ICTs in learning process is the lowest. However, in general, the mean numbers for all the four perspectives are above 3.9, high enough to conclude that first-year non-English major students strongly believe that the application of PBL at the school has a significant impact on their autonomy in learning English.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of mean numbers of the four dimensions of LA

Dimensions of LA	Mean
Initiating learning process	4.13
Monitoring learning process	4.04
Evaluating learning process	3.95
Using ICTs in learning process	3.92

5 CONCLUSION

The study aimed at finding out the perceptions of first-year non-English major students towards four dimensions of learner autonomy through Project-based learning at TDTU. A questionnaire with 24 questions was employed in the study. Data analysis with mean numbers of each question item has proved that most students show their positive attitudes towards project-based learning and its effects on their autonomy. According to the survey, Initiating learning progress was rated the highest among the four dimensions of learner autonomy by the students while Using ICTs in learning process was the lowest. It can be seen that students are clearly aware of initiating their learning process but applying ICT in learning English is still limited to certain extent.

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